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TOWARDS MULTIDISCIPLINARY ENGINEERING CURRICULUM DESIGN: A PILOT STUDY TO TEACH CONTROL EDUCATION IN MECHANICAL ENGINEERING WITH MATLAB/SIMULINK AND ARDUINO

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ABSTRACT

Current challenges in engineering curriculum design, face the necessity of a multidisciplinary approach due to the increasing complexity of engineering problems. Students need to be exposed to a multidisciplinary environment and, on the other hand, it is necessary to ensure the teaching of all the fundamentals of each engineering within the respective curriculum.

As an example, the contribution of automatic control to engineering has become a recognized pillar among the fundamental disciplines in engineering education. However, the instructors teaching control courses to students belonging to other engineering degrees than automation, must design a syllabus providing the right balance between fundamental theory and practical applications. To overcome these problems, we propose a novel approach consisting in the introduction of hands-on

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activities based on an Arduino engineering kit to teach control systems to mechanical engineering students.

The novelty of this pilot study consists of bringing such a practical approach to the laboratory classes of robotics and mechatronics within the mechanical engineering curriculum involving also basic concepts of electronics and data acquisition and processing through the interaction with sensors and actuators as well as programming skills to implement the control algorithms on the Arduino device.

This experience proved to be successful in helping students to maximize progress and build an effective comprehension of crucial engineering topics. It also showed that the hardware is appropriate to demonstrate and apply core learning principles. Moreover, it can be considered as a benchmark with potential effectiveness also in other courses and curricula. By realizing this approach, we envision that engineering education will be able to build important skills necessary to break down the walls between disciplines, enable cross-collaboration, produce well-rounded students, and increase employability opportunities.

1 INTRODUCTION

The more industry grows and evolves, the more professional engineers must develop working skills and knowledge beyond their original discipline due to the requirements of their employment. The risk is that most engineering graduates, although technically competent, do not have enough practical nor complementary professional skills required for working successfully in the workplace. The solution to address this issue needs to consider rethinking engineering curricula design as to increase their multidisciplinary. However, a common understanding on how to effectively do so has not been reached yet. Successful strategies may be identified in the adoption of maker projects, or the use of professional tools within laboratory activities of each curriculum.

As a pilot study to demonstrate this statement, we shall consider teaching of control theory in a mechanical engineering curriculum that, despite it has been pervading almost all subjects of higher learning, it is usually only available to students at the end of the undergraduate education and, most importantly, it typically stops at a theoretical level. Consequently, control theory practical applications remain unfamiliar to mechanical engineering students, who lack of a general comprehension of how control systems permeate a great variety of aspects regarding mechanical systems. This problem may find its roots in early tendencies in education promoting training approaches aimed at preparing high specialized students with deep competences but focused on a narrow spectrum of topics, in opposition to the current view supporting the need of interdisciplinary professional profiles, able to adapt to a wide scenario of situations and able to solve a variety of issues not strictly related to their specific area of expertise. Moreover, building hands-on experience about control theory problems in study programs falling outside automation engineering is usually overshadowed by the need to include core-teachings of those curricula. It is also worth considering that an effective laboratory of control theory builds on the foundations of statics and dynamics, circuit theory, signal processing

and programming coursework. Providing such a practical experience is often a great aid for teaching difficult concepts, but, on the other hand, forcing a hands-on approach can distract students from theoretical learning if they are unprepared [1]. This might be the case of undergraduate mechanical engineering students, who have a limited educational experience in control theory and are typically lacking in one or more of the above-mentioned foundations.

To address this need of a successful and feasible laboratory activity, aimed at teaching control theory at mechanical engineering students, this paper proposes a case study in which a project-based learning approach [2], [3], consisting on the use of maker projects, was applied to a conventional laboratory of robotics and mechatronics of the mechanical engineering curriculum at the University of Bologna, Italy. Specifically, this approach aimed at filling the gap between the competences in hardware development, widely taught in the mechanical engineering curriculum, and the actual lack of confidence with software development for mechanical system control, which is crucial to form students with a comprehensive perspective. Project-based learning consists of a model that organizes learning around projects grounded in the theoretical background of constructivism, a learning theory that perceives learning as a process of constructing knowledge based on experience [4]. In project-based learning, students are engaged in diverse components of problem solving, interdisciplinary curriculum, open-ended questions, hands-on activities, group work, and interactive group activities [5], [6].

We investigated to what extent a kit developed by Arduino in collaboration with MathWorks, can be successfully used in a project-based module, to enable mechanical engineering students grasping fundamental control principles [7], [8]. Our idea is that such an approach allows for students or student teams to design smart solutions, experience input-output systems with data gathering, decision rules and output commands. Also, it may encourage students to increase their awareness and perception of control topics, improving their engagement and the learning itself.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Experimental set-up

The project was based on a kit, developed by Arduino in partnership with MathWorks, aimed at providing a hands-on educational approach for students. The idea behind this kit is to enable college students and educators to incorporate core engineering concepts into their Arduino projects with the support of MATLAB and Simulink programming, thanks to industry-standard tools for algorithm development, system modeling, simulation and robotics, all of which will be required in their future careers [9].

Arduino is an open-source hardware, software, and content platform with a worldwide community of over 30 million active users. It has powered thousands of projects over the years, from everyday objects to complex scientific instruments. MATLAB is a programming platform specifically designed for engineering and scientific computing. The MATLAB Support Package for Arduino enables the user to

communicate with Arduino hardware directly in MATLAB. Users can interactively read data from a variety of sensors and peripheral devices, process raw data into meaningful values, and actuate external devices. Simulink is a block diagram environment for modeling and simulating dynamic systems, which supports developing algorithms that can be embedded into Arduino and other hardware. The Simulink Support Package for Arduino extends Simulink with blocks for configuring Arduino sensors, as well as reading and writing data from them. After creating a Simulink model, users can run the simulation and interactively tune algorithm parameters in order to meet the expected result. Through automatic code generation, the Arduino support package removes the need to write C or C++ code. That also means that users don't need to compile and build an application for it to run. Users can then download the completed algorithm for stand-alone execution on an Arduino device.

The specific application proposed in this project consisted in assembling a self-balancing motorcycle, which can maneuver on its own on various terrains and remain upright using a flywheel for balance (see Figure1 (a) and (b)). The Arduino Engineering Kit includes step-by-step instructions and lessons, featuring a short introduction, a getting-started guide for the tools that will be used, a concepts section, and finally the projects themselves. The robot is controlled by a series of Arduino boards (MKR1000, MKR Motor Shield, MKR IMU Shield (see Figure1 (c)), several customized parts, and a complete set of electrical and mechanical components (a DC motor with encoder, a standard micro servo, a hall sensor module, an ultrasonic sensor and a speedometer).

Figure 1: a) the self-balancing motorcycle of the Arduino engineering kit; b) Study of vehicles kinematics' and dynamics in order to design a model; c) The set of the three Arduino boards (MKR1000, MKR Motor Shield, MKR IMU Shield) controlling the robot

2.2 Learning activity

Students were requested to create models for the control of the hardware components and to design and run a hardware-in-the-loop simulation to tune and validate the controller's parameters in order to improve the developed algorithms. Instructions to students were also to program the control algorithm in MATLAB and Simulink, which can easily interface with Arduino, thanks to the already available support packages.

The laboratory experience with such as Arduino engineering kit consisted in two phases: in a first, step students had to study the vehicles kinematics and dynamics in order to design its model (see Figure 1) and, in a second phase, they had to implement such model in Simulink and simultaneously assemble the hardware components. The two phases continuously interchanged during the development process, as students chose to follow a step by step approach in which they evaluated the implemented changes in the controller by simulating them in Simulink.

3 RESULTS

All students successfully completed the project-based module, and reported that this activity certainly facilitated a better understanding of the theoretical concepts of control theory that were covered along the project. Also, they reported Simulink to be user-friendly and flexible (also for real-time applications), oriented to components safety and effective in controlling the inertia wheel. They also identified some future applications and developments, specifically consisting in the implementation of an algorithm for the self-calibration of the IMU in real time, the development of an algorithm for pre-defined trajectories and possible improvements in the algorithm for obstacles avoidance.

Overall, what students learned during this hands-on activity, can be summarized as follows:

- Modelling and simulation of the the dynamic system's behavior in Simulink (Figure 2)
- Application of custom algorithms for complex math operations, and PID control
- Incorporation of logic-based algorithms that define system behavior for different states (e.g. move forward, turn, stop)
- Building and running a working Arduino application from a Simulink model; connecting MATLAB and Simulink to the Arduino MKR1000 and reading/writing of data from connected sensors (encoders, IMU, hall sensor) and actuators (DC motors, servo motor); tuning and optimizing Simulink model parameters as the application is running on Arduino
- Analyzing and visualizing data from Arduino

Figure 2: Overview of the Simulink model controlling the self-balancing motorcycle. Model subsystems comprise, from left to right, the IMU capturing the inclination angle (red), the controller generating the torque command (blue), the obstacle avoidance algorithm

The case study presented here provides evidence of effectiveness and feasibility of applying a project-based learning approach to teach control theory in the laboratory of robotics and mechatronics in a mechanical engineering course. This approach, based on the Arduino Engineering Kit programmed with MATLAB/Simulink, proved to be suitable for future uses in additional modules, as it kept students motivated and engaged and, most importantly, it appeared to be highly effective in delivering complex theoretical concepts, otherwise difficult to grasp.

4 CONCLUSION

An essential aspect to consider in the design of engineering curricula is that at the end of the course students preparation meets industry demands. Indeed, the skills and knowledge that engineering students acquire during their studies play an important role in their employability and ultimately their success. As a matter of fact, employers are finding it progressively more difficult to employ engineering graduates who can be productive and master design tasks, methodologies and tools with minimal retraining. To maintain a healthy flow of new graduates into industry, a systematic approach is required to bridge the gap between employer expectations and graduates' skills. In order to fill the gap between the necessity of engineering curricula to teach multidisciplinary and practical skills, and the need to identifying the still missing best practices to reach these objectives, we proposed the implementation of laboratory activities based on maker projects to teach control in mechanical engineering. From this study it emerged how the use of such cutting-edge Arduino-based project allowed students to easily learn fundamental engineering concepts, key aspects of mechatronics, such as MATLAB and Simulink programming. Millions of engineers and scientists in various industries and academia

use MATLAB for a range of applications, including deep learning and machine learning, signal processing and communications, image and video processing, control systems, and many more. Also, in this specific application, students could exploit the functionality of MATLAB/Simulink of being a high-level language, thanks to which users can see results immediately from I/O instructions without having to compile code and thus, allowing them to just focus on the engineering modelling and design. Another aspect to consider is that an effective control education course is yet to be defined, and successful study plans are still under investigation [10]. What emerged to be clear, however, is the need to foster the acquisition of appropriate technical skills by ensuring a combination of fundamental theory and practical applications, overcoming the constraints imposed by the very limited time span that needs to include lectures, labs and exercises [11].

We here exploited the positive effect of practical experiences on the learning process, well established since the early theories on experiential learning [12] by implementing hands on activities based on a Arduino engineering kit programmed with MATLAB and Simulink to teach control systems to mechanical engineering students. The novelty of this pilot study consisted in bringing such a practical learning approach to the laboratory classes of robotics and mechatronics within the mechanical engineering curriculum, which up to now was only limited to a theoretical overview of control topics.

This experience proved to be successful in helping students to maximize progresses and build an effective comprehension of crucial topics otherwise of difficult understanding. Indeed, students were also exposed and needed to solve also basic problems concerning electronics and data acquisition and processign throught the interaction with sensors and actuators as well as programming aspects to implement the control alogorithms on the Arduino device.

It also emerged how hardware is appropriate to demonstrate and apply core learning principles.

Such proposal is to be considered as a benchmark with high scalability potential and we envision it might have a similar feasibility and effectiveness also in other engineering courses, not only for advanced students, but also during the early years at university.

In fact, it may substantially help teaching of introductory courses that up to date still challenges academics trying to identify what resources to use, what topics to include, how to assess or teach and, more specifically, what examples would constitute expected levels of performance and comprehension. Indeed, this case study provides project description, simulation software, and code so that academics can quickly and easily include them in their own teaching. By realizing this approach we envision that engineering education will be able to build important skills necessary to break down the walls between disciplines, enable cross-collaboration, produce well-rounded students, and increase employability opportunities.

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